

Vegetative Vascular Dystonia Syndrome in School-Aged Children

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 4 Sep 2024; **Published:** 10 Oct 2024

Abstract: The article is devoted to vegetative vascular dystonia and the symptoms and causes of this syndrome in children of school age. It is a pity that in the current era of globalization, all of us, especially children, are living in unhealthy environmental conditions and victims of technology. As a result of these factors, it is a fact that various diseases are spreading. Vegetative vascular dystonia syndrome is one of them. Currently, the widespread prevalence of this syndrome in approximately 85% of school-aged children indicates the relevance of the topic, its complications and damage to the systems necessary for life activities and the educational process.

Keywords: Dystonia, Dysfunction, Stress, Depression, Neurosis, Neurotic-paroxysmal, Sympathetic, Parasympathetic, Thermoregulation, ECG.

Vegetative vascular dystonia syndrome is a functional disorder caused by the disturbance of vascular tone rhythm by the vegetative nervous system. It is manifested by severe or constant nervousness, strong sweating, headache, facial redness and sweating, discoloration and fainting. Neuroses lead to constant arterial hypertension, affecting the quality of life. Vegetative vascular dystonia can be caused by any specific pathologies, so it is not considered an independent disease in modern medicine. Vegetative vascular dystonia syndromes can be found in the medical literature. For example, vegetative dysfunction, angioneurosis, psychovegetative neurosis, vasomotor dystonia, vegetative dystonia syndrome. 30 years ago, autonomic vascular dystonia was a very rare syndrome. Today, according to statistics, more than 75% of people on our planet are affected by this disease at some level. Most of them do not receive medical help, because the symptoms of the syndrome improve, but on average 1/3 of patients need treatment and therapeutic and neurological support. The clinical theory of the pathology of the autonomic nervous system is connected with the names of N. Eppinger, L. Hess, who created the idea of the pathology of the autonomic nervous system. Taking into account the division of the syndrome of vegetative dystonia into sympathetic and parasympathetic parts, a second general vegetative syndrome, sympathikonia, soon appeared. Vegetative vascular dystonia is a dysfunction of two nervous systems, the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems. The generalization of individual autonomic disorders in these syndromes contributed to the development of clinical autonomic disorders. There are some situations that require attention. Symptoms of vegetative-vascular dystonia, firstly, pathological syndromes have not yet formed and, on the contrary, reflect certain, often constitutional features of the organization and reaction of the autonomic nervous system; Secondly, they fully reflected the manifestation of the general syndrome of vegetative dystonia of greater

severity; Thirdly, in these definitions, the symptoms of vegetative-vascular dystonia are very important when they are combined with personality traits and emotional reactions. The first signs of vegetative dystonia occur in childhood and adulthood. Expressive changes appear between the ages of 20 and 40, women are 3 times more prone to it than men. Another relevance of the problem of vegetative-vascular dystonia is that many general practitioners are not sufficiently familiar with the manifestations of psychopathological diseases, this syndrome often forms functional vegetative disorders. This situation can lead to wrong diagnosis and wrong treatment.

Vegetative vascular dystonia occurs mainly among young people. Since it is manifested as a clinical syndrome of various diseases, there are no accurate statistical data on its distribution among the population.

What are the main causes of vegetative vascular dystonia syndrome?

- First of all, the imbalance between the sympathetic and parasympathetic effects of the nervous system causes the development of vegetative vascular dystonia.
- Vegetative vascular dystonia in young children can appear as a result of pathologies of the perinatal period, birth trauma, neonatal diseases. These factors have a negative impact on the formation of the somatic and vegetative nervous system and the integration of the functions that replace them. In children of this type, there is a tendency to vegetative dysfunction, digestive disorders, and emotional lability.
- At the age of puberty, the development of internal organs and the growth of the body usually occur before the formation of neuroendocrine regulation. This causes the development of vegetative dysfunction.
- At a certain age, vegetative vascular dystonia is manifested by pain, nervousness, decreased arterial pressure, psychoneurological diseases (high fatigue, decreased attention and vigilance, high level of excitability, nervousness).
- In some people, vegetative vascular dystonia can be manifested as a complication of chronic diseases, depression, stress, neurosis, brain trauma, and endocrine diseases.
- Complex psychosomatic diseases;
- Hypertension;
- Obesity;
- Heart failure;
- Inability to occupy the child's psychological and physical place in society;
- Periodic crises - temporary exacerbation of symptoms (sharp deterioration of physical well-being and emotional state)

The autonomic nervous system is responsible for unconscious regulation of several important processes. They are:

- Normalization of blood pressure, vascular system.
- Heart rate, contraction frequency.
- Secretory activity of the glands.
- Normalization of the motor functions of the small and large intestine, gall bladder, smooth muscles.
- Under the influence of both internal and external negative factors, subsystems stop working in coordination and start working independently of each other. This is how a

syndrome called vegetative vascular dystonia develops.

What are nervous system disorders like?

- The functions of the sympathetic nervous system are regulated by the sympathoadrenal system, which controls the sympathetic through the production of adrenaline and norepinephrine. An increase in the amount of catecholamine hormones, their concentration, suppresses crises. Tachycardia can cause shortness of breath and dizziness. All these signs develop quickly and cause inexplicable fear in a person. It can be repeated over and over again for many years. This exhausts the nervous system of patients.

Vegetative vascular dystonia can develop on the other hand. The parasympathetic nervous system works depending on the activity of special nerve fibers.

There are many types of symptoms, but the most common are:

- ✓ Cardiological symptoms:
- ✓ Tachycardia and arrhythmia (heart contraction and increased heart rate)
- ✓ Bradycardia and arrhythmia with a decrease in heart rate Pain and spasms in the heart, pressure.
- ✓ Increased vascular tone - hypertension,
- ✓ Decreased vascular tone - hypotension,
- ✓ Increased blood pressure,
- ✓ Hyperemia of the skin or its opposite - cyanosis,
- ✓ difficulty breathing shortness of breath,
- ✓ A feeling of swelling in the throat, difficulty in swallowing food and liquids.
- ✓ Gastrointestinal symptoms,
- ✓ indigestion or diarrhea,
- ✓ Fatigue apathy,
- ✓ Symptoms of hypochondria, minor unpleasant complaints,
- ✓ Depressive states. Irritability, aggression, periodic headaches,
- ✓ Sleep disturbance .

Vegetative vascular dystonia can be caused by acute and chronic stress that causes anxiety and depression. Long-term family disputes, social unrest, severe somatic diseases act as stress. Vegetative vascular dystonia occurs during hormonal changes, puberty, menopause. The intensity of vegetative reactions is associated with a new level of endocrine activity of the body. This syndrome accompanies all serious neurological diseases (Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, consequences of severe brain diseases). Vegetative vascular dystonia is often associated with neurosis, which is characterized by a decrease in the energy potential of the brain and a violation of adaptive reactions.

As mentioned above, vegetative vascular dystonia leads to severe complications. One of the main causes of it is stress. It is very important that we, as pedagogues, do our part to prevent this. For this, pedagogues They should have information about dystonia, its signs and causes, and methods of working with children with this syndrome.

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